

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INSTAGRAM CAPTIONS IN ENHACING STUDENTS' WRITING

Nur Azizah

Sekolah Tinggi Agama Islam Mempawah
Noerazizah.al2124@gmail.com

Abstract

The aim of this research was to enhancing students' writing skill in third semester by adding Instagram caption on the students' process in teaching and learning. The design of this research was descriptive qualitative research to describe the effectiveness of Instagram captions to enhacing students' writing skill in third semester of Tadris English language. The research was conducted as Sekolah Tinggi Agama Islam mempawah in academic year 2024-2025. It was selected by the researcher based on the background of the students knowledge in writing skill. In this research, the researchen found that the students face some difficulties in writing English text. In collecting data, the researcher used were observation and interview the students in third semester. The observation one class only. Most of the students in the classroom are eight students. Three students male and five students are female. The researcher found that the students still difficult to write in some sentencess especially make a caption in their status story in Instagram. The puppose of this research is to find out the effectiveness of Instagram caption in increasing students writing skill. Based on the explanation and result of the student's write caption on Instagram, the researcher found that writing captions on Instagram is indeed effective in improving student's writing skill.

Keywords: *Instagram, caption, and writing skill,*

Introduction

Digital social media is one of a popular platform for people komunication, interaction, and sharing or gate information particularly Gen Z and Gen Alpha generations. Gen Z means who group of people grow up with modern technology as like smartphone, social media, and the internet making them extremely comfortable with it. They used it to update their story status and write a caption bellow the picture or video, they can share the knowledge, keep track of others, and engage in virtual social interactions. Especially generation Z students. They can spend the time by scrolling as like instagram. It means that the students can explore anything they want in social media, especially instagram.

Instagram is on of the social media that can students used to communicate and share the knowledge by adding stoty status. Many of the students used instagram to create their activities in real life or just to scrolling only to get some information in

instagram. According to a report by Kepios, the number of global instagram user reached 1.74 billion as of February 2025. The result suggest that Instagram is one of the most popular social media platforms worldwide. Indonesia in 2025 the number of Instagram users is approximately 90,183,200 which accounts for 31,8 percent of the country's total population. From the result about show that the Instagram is on of the popular social media in this word.

Musonera stated that Instagram can help students recognize how the social media impacts companies, businesses and our daily lives. To give the students opportunity to develop and assess marketing strategies and competitive forces in the social media. To help students understand how the social media presents the market opportunity for advertisers and other businesses. To offer students the opportunity to analyze how social media impact company strategies.

Instagram has many feature that can used by people aspecially students. Julius stated that Instagram has become a global phenomenon with billions of active users every month, with its innovative features, Instagram has successfully created an immersive experience of diverse photos and video. It means that the students can be creative to make a video or take a pictutes by features in Instahram.

The feature in Instagram are: The first the students can make photos and videos. Second the students can using filters and effect that can be used to enhance the photo or vidioes more beatifull than before. Third, the students can give comments and likes other users' posts. Four, is followers and following. It means that, the students can follow others account to see their posts in their feed. Five is instagram storie. It is the features allows users to share the beatiful photos or video that are only available for 24 hours. Six is instagram live. Sevent is reels and the las is IGTV. IGTV means is the students can upload longer videos than regular posts.

The benefit of instagram to make the students creative and increase their writing skill are; the students can sharing experiences or moment with other people. The students can building comunicaties in Instagram with other people who share similar interests. The students can make Instagram to promoting their business. the students can following celebrities and influencers. The last is the students can post their photos to the public to make their existence or just for fun in social media and get comments from their followers. Transinata (2019) stated that using photo based media on Instagram social media can improve students' writing skill and effect to use English.

The students can write a captions below photos or video to explain what happen in photos or video. Daud (2018) said that caption in Instagram is some sentences for clarifying the images or videos that want to post. On Instagram, caption turns into extensive thing because the users want to give Instagram or messages

about what users' feeling and doing. It is make the students' writing improve. Besides that Nabila (2022) stated that caption is a text that aims to describe a picture or photo so that the picture or the photo more interesting.

Daud (2018) Stated that social media is not only give function to make the user have fun, but it is also profitable for education especially in educate students in writing. It means that social media can make the students' writing skill increase. Aprilia et al state that writing is essential because it helps students to communicate their thoughts, feelings, and experiences in specific places and situations.

Writing is the process of creating written content, such as text, messages, letter or caption. It is a form of communication or sharing knowledge that involves conveying thoughts, ideas, and messages through written language. Writing can help the students to process and retain information better. By putting their thought into words they reinforce their understanding of the subject matter. Writing can help the students easy to write a caption in Instagram status story. It is make the students can explore their ideas and information in caption of the Instagram story. Purba et al (2021) stated that writing is an instrument for thinking and learning and the way to explore ideas or information. It means that the students can explore their imagination through writing. It is very clear, that can help students improve their writing skills.

The researcher as the English teacher used Instagram as media to make the students' writing skill improve. Based on the result of students writing task. The researcher found some problems that relate to increase students' writing skill. It means that from the eight students in third semester only three students in good writing. Five students less of the writing.

Based on the result of students interview, the researcher found that the students less of vocabulary, less grammatical, and the students did not enjoy when learning English because the students did not understand and many of vocabulary unfamiliar with the students. Based on the explanation above the researcher want to enhancing students' writing skill by Instagram in third semester. The aim of this research is to enhancing the students writing skill based on the effectiveness of Instagram in teaching and learning English.

METHOD

In this research, the researcher applied descriptive qualitative research to describe the effectiveness of Instagram captions to enhancing students' writing skill in third semester of Tadris English language. Qualitative research is a method that the researcher used to make this research complete explanation. Creswell (2012) stated that qualitative research is an obtain research useful for exploration and

understanding a central phenomenon. In qualitative research the researcher interprets the meaning of the information, drawing on personal reflections and past research.

Moser and korsrjens (2017) stated that qualitative research is a type of research that explores and provides deeper insights into real world problem without having to quantitative data. It means that qualitative research is a method that can be used by researcher to solve the problem and explain the detail description without using numeric data or testing hypotheses. Additionally Oranga and Materi (2023) stated that qualitative research is to explore and provide deeper, comprehensive and detailed description of phenomena from non-numeric data, rather than quantifying and testing hypotheses using numeric data as is the case with quantitative research. It means that the qualitative research is to investigated and interprets connections, individual experience, and collective behaviors.

The research was conducted as Sekolah Tinggi Agama Islam mempawah in academic year 2024-2025. It was selected by the researcher based on the background of the students knowledge in writing skill. In this research, the researcher found that the students face some difficulties in writing English text. Thus, the researcher intended to overcome the students difficulties by using Instagram caption. The objective of this research is to explain the effectiveness of Instagram caption in increasing the student's writing skill in third semester academic years 2024-2025.

In collecting data, the researcher used were observation and interview the students in third semester. The observation one class only. Most of the students in the classroom are eight students. Three students male and five students are female. The researcher found that the students still difficult to write in some sentences especially make a caption in their status story in Instagram. Base on the observation three students has good writing skill, because they are mastered some of the vocabulary at their level, it would be easier to write some sentences in Instagram caption and five students still less.

The interview is used unstructured interview to get free information based on the students answers about Instagram caption. The data was gained from the English teacher as the researcher of sentence structure in writing, grammar, vocabulary and how much students do to write a caption for their story status in Instagram. The researcher want to know how often the students write English caption in their Instagram. For writing test are carried out for one semester, it is six months.

Findings

This regard attempted to describe the effectiveness of using Instagram caption in increasing student's writing skill third semester in Sekolah Tinggi Agama Islam

Mempawah, especially Tadris English language academic year 2024-2025. The number of the students in the classroom are eight students. The purpose of this research is to find out the effectiveness of Instagram caption in increasing students writing skill. Based on the explanation and result of the student's write caption on Instagram, the researcher found that writing captions on Instagram is indeed effective in improving student's writing skill.

The finding of this research deal with the complete explanation based on the student's interview and the result of student's writing caption in Instagram. This research indicates positive respont from the students. As the result of student's caption shows that most of the students used Instagram and what they write a captions. Caption writing begins in the second meeting of a process teaching and leaning in the classroom until one semester or six months. Students write captions twice a week, namely on Saturday night and Sunday night. The topic of the caption is based on to the picture or video uploaded by the students in Instagram as the media.

After the students write a caption, they are get likes and comments from their followers on Instagram, it is make the students get feedback from their followers while, the teacher corrects the students' writing. Moreover, the result of the students write a caption it can be discuss together in the classroom. Are there any instances of incorrect writing, unfamiliar word or similar word that the other students did not know. What the teacher corrects are the writing structure and grammar as well as the accuracy of writing captions and photos or videos. Besides, the student's thinking were increasing since the students have already gotten used writing caption on Instagram as the media that they used to improve their writing skill.

Below are some examples of captions from the students for one semester or six months. The result of students writing can be randomly selected based on the month they uploaded in Instagram.

Picture 2.1 (Students English caption in their Instahram

Based on one of the students caption above show “when the rainbow comes, don’t forget tha umbrella that accompanies you when its rains. Don;t forget the rain because without rain you won’t find your rainbow”. The researcher found grammatical errors in the result of the students writing caption on Instagram. But the researcher as the lecture has recomendation in specific style preference or want further refinements. This version can works better;

“ When the rainbow comes”. The word of “comes” can change to be “appears”, it is more natural and visually expressive. Example, “ When the rainbow appears”.

“The umbrella that accompanies you”, to be “The umbrella that sheltered you”.

Word of “Shetered” makes the sentence more vivid and meaningfull.

The last comment is about grammatical of the “When it rained” instead of “when its rains”. It is show there is grammatical because there is no consistency past tentse.

From the explanation above, it shows that social media from Instagram has an effect on students' writing results. Seen from the results of students' writing skill from the first time they made captions in English language until the last month of the semester they wrote captions in English on their Instagram. The students got a lot of new vocabulary building, it is unfamiliar or familiar with the students through writing caption on Instagram. the students also improve their grammatical. In the and, the students could self their confidences in exploring and showing to the public through Instagram.

Conclusion

After explanation about the effectiveness of Instagram caption, the researcher concluded that Instagram caption can increase the student’s writing skill in third semester Sekolah Tinggi Agama Islam Mempawah, tadris English language. It was proven by the result of students’ writing during one semester or six month. The students could get feedback by their followers when they are write a caption based on their photos or video in Instagram. in addition, the students could improve their critical thingking. It is based on the interview to get free information based on the students answers about Instagram caption. The data was gained from the English teacher as the researcher of sentence sturcture in writing, grammar, vocabulary and how much students do to write a caption for their story status in Instagram. The researcher want

to know how often the students write English caption in their Instagram. For writing test are carried out for one semester, it is six months.

Instagram was proven as one of the alternative social media that can be used by the students to increase their writing skill. As well, The students got a lot of new vocabulary building, it is unfamiliar or familiar with the students through writing caption on Instagram. The students could practice to improving their writing skill on Instagram through writing caption. It also make the students a change to build their knowledge on Instagram. Instagram as the media can give contribution in student's writing skill. The aim of this research is to enhancing the students writing skill based on the effectiveness of Instagram in teaching and learning English.

Reference

- Aprilia, R, at al. 2022. *The Effect Of Instagram On Students' Writing Skill In Recount Text*. English Educational Department, STKIP PGRI Bangkalan
- Creswell, J.W. (2012). *Educational Research*. Boston: Person Education.
- Daud, D. 2018. *Utilizing Instagram Caption To Improve Students Ability In Writing Descriptive Text*. English Education Department Faculty Of Teacher Training And Education Muhammadiyah University Of Makassar.
- Julius, N. 2025. The Number of Data Instagram Users In Indonesia 2025. <https://upgraded.id/data-jumlah-pengguna-instagram-di-indonesia>.
- Moser, A. and Korstjens, I. (2017) Series: Practical Guidance to Qualitative Research. Part 3: Sampling, Data Collection and Analysis. *European Journal of General Practice*, 24, 9-18
- Musonera, E. 2018. *Instagram: Photo Sharing Application*. Mercer University
- Oranga, J. And Matere, A. 2023. *Qualitative Research: Essence, Types and Advantages*. Kisii University, Kenya
- Purba, R. At all. (2021). Improving Students' Writing Skill Through Instagram Stories. Vol. 9 No. 4
- Transinata, D. A. 2019. *Writing Caption on Instagram as Media fo Student's Motivation and Writing Skill Improvement*. *English Teaching Journal*. https://www.google.com/search?q=jumlah+pengguna+instagram+di+dunia&sca_esv=co655b8860eb5549&sxsrf=AHTn8zrEdb46RWJMuVst7ouWitHyl-